

The Non-Negative Negator in Mandarin Chinese and “Neg-Cleft”

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1. Introduction

The paper syntactically investigates a colloquial Mandarin construction that involves a N(on)-N(egating) N(egator). In (1), the negator *bù* (不) does not negate the proposition, but rather adds a mood (marked as +M) such that the speaker thinks what he says should be known by the speech participants.¹ As seen in (1), *bù* can be followed by the copula *shì*, and at the end of the sentence is an optional particle *ma* (嘛).^{2,3} It is crucial to note that (1) is not a biased question. A biased question has a rising intonation and requests for a response. (1) in contrast has a falling intonation and is assertive.

- (1) Tā ⟨bù/ bú-shì⟩ yǐjīng zǒu-le (ma). ↘
3SG NNN NNN-COP already leave-PERF PRT
‘He already left. +M’

The NNN occurs also in varying syntactic positions. As seen in (2), the NNN can either be clause-second, or be put sentence-initially or sentence finally. In the presence of *ma*, the NNN can either precede or follow it. Note that in some positions, the NNN’s being followed by a copula is preferred.

- (2) ?{bu(-shi)} Tā {bu(-shi)} yǐjīng zǒu-le ({bu*(-shi)} ma) {bu*?(-shi)}.
NNN(-COP) 3SG already leave-PERF PRT
‘He already left. +M’

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. In §2, I go through several important properties of the NNN, especially those that distinguish it from the regular usage of the negator, and in §3 I depict the syntactic analysis and shows that the NNN construction must involve a ‘Neg-cleft’. §4 lays out some predictions that the ‘Neg-cleft’ analysis correctly makes, and §5 concludes the paper and discusses some implications and remaining questions.

¹ I use Pinyin for Mandarin, Yale Romanisation for Korean and IPA (Chen& Gussenhoven 2015) for Shanghainese. The abbreviations are as follows: C=complementiser, CLT=clitic, COP=copula, DAT=dative, DEC=declarative, PERF=perfect, PL=plural, FUT=future tense, PROG=progressive, PRT=particle, NNN=Non-Negative Negator, SG=singular.

² *shi* feeds the sandhi of *bù*, turning it into *bú*. The tone marker of *bù/bú* is omitted in the environment *bu(-shi)*.

³ Some native speakers do not like the deletion of the copula *shì*, whilst most speakers I consulted that are in their early twenties that *shì* is always deletable after the NNN. A geographical and generational gap seems to exist.

2. Properties of the NNN

There are several important properties of the NNN. First, the NNN is immune to the so called *Neg Neg constraint (Collins 2018). In (3), a NegP dominating another NegP in English leads to ungrammaticality. This constraint exists also in Mandarin as (4a) shows. To make (4a) acceptable, one has to incorporate a cleft by using the copula *shì* to prevent the two NegP's from being too close, seen in (4b). However, the NNN superficially escapes the *Neg Neg Constraint. As (5) shows, the NNN can precede another negator felicitously even without a copula.

(3) *He is very not not happy. (COLLINS 2018:6)

(4) a. *Tā **bú-bù**-kāixīn. (*[NegP**bú** [NegP**bù** ...]])
 3SG NEG-NEG-happy
 Intended: 'He is not not happy.'

b. ✓ Tā bú-shì bù-kāixīn. (✓[NegP**bú** [CopP**shì** ...[NegP**bù** ...]])
 3SG NEG-COP NEG-happy
 'It is not the case he is not happy.'

(5) ✓ Tā **bu(-shì) bù** kāixīn (ma).
 3SG NNN(-COP) NEG happy PRT
 'He is not happy. +M'

Second, the NNN is different from the regular negator in terms of sandhi. The regular *bù* is a lexically marked tone-sandhi element (Chang 1992, Chen 2000). As shown in (6), the negator is phonologically realised as *bú* (rising tone) with the falling tone, and as *bù* (falling tone) under other circumstances. The regular negator in (7) must be pronounced as *bú*, not *bù*, even if there is an intervening pause as happens, for example, when the speaker enunciates the sentence verbatim in an angry mood. However, this sandhi is not obligatory on the NNN. Seen in (8), the NNN (when not followed by *shì*) can either have the rising tone as triggered by the following *huì*, or keep the default falling tone.

(6) a.

bù-huī	bù-huí	bù-huǐ	bú -huì
NEG-wave	NEG-return	NEG-destroy	NEG-will

b. [NEG] ⇒ /bú/ / _51
 ⇒ /bù/ / Elsewhere

(7) Tā **⟨bú/*bù⟩** (||) huì qù Shǒuěr.
 3SG NEG will go Seoul
 'He won't go to Seoul.'

(8) Tā **⟨✓bú/✓bù⟩** huì qù Shǒuěr (ma). (optional sandhi)
 3SG NNN will go Seoul PRT
 'He will go to Seoul. +M'

Third, the NNN can be used only in the matrix clause. (9) shows a felicitous case of embedding of the regular negator, whilst the NNN is a main clause phenomenon. Forced embedding of the NNN under locutive verbs like *shuō* “say” or doxastic verbs like *juéde* “think” in (10), with the mood +M intended to reside in the subject’s mental state, leads to a direct quotation reading. This is guaranteed by the fact that the first pronoun *wǒ* in (10) refers to *Zhāngsān* with the embedded deixis logophorically anchored to the matrix subject instead of the speaker. The NNN’s non-embeddability distinguishes it in distribution from Expletive Negation, or what Yoon (2011) calls Evaluative Negation, found in many languages whereby the negator can be well embedded, be it under a negative predicate as in (11a) or a positive one as (11b) showcases. Note especially that in the Korean example (11b), the first person pronoun *naykey* refers to the speaker (Lee 2023, *p.c.*) with no indexical shift.

- (9) Zhāngsān ⟨shuō/ juéde⟩ [CP *wǒ* **bú**-huì qù Shǒuěr].
 say think 1SG NEG-will go Seoul
 ‘Zhāngsān ⟨said/thought⟩ that I wouldn’t go to Seoul.’
- (10) ?Zhāngsān ⟨shuō/ juéde⟩ [CP=Direct Quotation *wǒ* **bu(-shì)** huì qù Shǒuěr (ma)].
 say think 1SG NNN(-COP) will go Seoul PRT
 ☑: ‘Zhāngsān ⟨said/thought⟩: “I[→Zhāngsān] will go to Seoul_{+M}”.’
 ☒: ‘Zhāngsān ⟨said/thought⟩_{+M} that I[→SPEAKER] would go to Seoul.’
- (11) a. Fovame **min** espasa to podhi mu. Greek
 fear NEG break the leg mine.CLT
 ‘I am afraid that I might have broke my leg.’ (MAKRI 2013: 12)
- b. Swuman-un Mina-ga *naykey* o-ci-**anh**-ul-kka kitayha-koiss-ta.
 -TOP -NOM 1SG.DAT COME-C-NEG-FUT-C_{nonfactive} hope-PROG-DEC Korean
 ‘Swuman hopes Mina will come to me[→SPEAKER].’ (YOON 2011: 116, adapted)

Fourth, the NNN is not recursive. While the regular negator which can be recursively used so long as the sentence is processable seen in (12), the NNN cannot be recursively used. (13a) and (13b) show that in this double subject (topic) sentence, the NNN might either follow the first subject *Zhāngsān* or the second subject *tóufǎ*, but using the NNN after each subject as in (13c) is ungrammatical. Readers might be curious why it is even necessary to point out the non-recursivity of the NNN, since it does not make obvious sense to recursively use the mood denoted by the NNN. The purpose is to show that not only is the NNN a matrix phenomenon, but it is morphologically exponenced only once without any negative concord effects.

- (12) Zhāngsān **bú**-shì tóufǎ **bù**-cháng, érshì ...
 NEG-COP hair NEG-long, instead
 ‘As for Zhāngsān, it is not the case that his hair is not long; instead ...’

- (13) a. Zhāngsān **bu(-shì)** tóufǎ hěn cháng (ma).
 NNN(-COP) hair very long PRT
 ‘As for Zhāngsān, his hair is very long. +M’
- b. Zhāngsān tóufǎ **bu(-shì)** hěn cháng (ma).
 hair NNN(-COP) very long PRT
- c. *Zhāngsān **bu(-shì)** tóufǎ **bu(-shì)** hěn cháng (ma).
 NNN(-COP) hair NNN(-COP) very long PRT

3. Syntactic Analysis

My syntactic analysis is shown in (14), the central argument being that the NNN construction involves a ‘Neg-cleft’ even when no copula is pronounced. The existence of a cleft is strongly supported by the absence of the *Neg Neg constraint and of the obligatory sandhi on the NNN. In the spirit of antihomophony (Kayne 2019), I argue that the NNN and the copula project NegP and CopP respectively above a PrP that relates the subject with a full-fledged CP.

That said, the non-negativeness of the NNN is not primitive, nor is the NNN an agreement marker triggered by a silent operator as found in negative concord languages (Zeijlstra 2007). The NNN is nothing but the same lexical item as the regular negator. If so, whence comes the non-negativeness? This is due to its position and the licensing of a Mood head. Before elaborating it in §4, I first give in (15) the derivation of (1), where the subject merges at spec,PrP below the NNN and moves to spec,TP for [EPP]-checking, and the TP then moves to spec,ForceP.

(15)

The otherword orders are accounted for by two variations: ① the phrasemoved to spec,ForceP; ② the EPP-satisfier. First, it might be the PrP instead of the TP that moves to spec,ForceP. Notice that (1) is often realised in casual speech as (16a) where the NNN along with the subject is stranded as depicted in (17a). Second, the matrix [EPP] is less preferably checked by a silent discourse anaphora THIS. We then would have a sentence initial NNN if the TP moves to spec,ForceP, and a sentence final (after *ma*) NNN if the PrP moves to spec,ForceP, whose derivations are shown respectively (SAP, MoodP omitted) in (17a) and (17b). The case where the NNN precedes by *ma* is derived by PrP to spec,TP and TP to spec,ForceP movement, seen in (17c). I offer no satisfactory answer at this moment to why this position of the NNN forces the copula to be pronounced overtly.

- (16) a. Yǐjīng zǒu-le ma tā bu(-shì).
 already leave-PERF PRT 3SG NNN-(COP)
 ‘He already left. +M’

b.

- (17) a. [ForceP [TP THIS [NegP **bu** [CopP(**shi**) [PrP THIS [CP 3SG₁ already left]]]]] [Force'(*ma*) t_{TP}]]
 b. [ForceP [PrP THIS [CP 3SG₁ already left]] [Force' (*ma*) [TP THIS [NegP **bu** [CopP(**shi**) t_{PrP}]]]]]
 c. [ForceP [TP [PrP 3SG₁ [CP *pro*₁ already left]] [T' [NegP **bu** [CopP **shi** t_{PrP}]]]] [Force'(*ma*) t_{TP}]]

It is crucial to add that (17c) is *not* a tag question though they happen to be similar on the surface. In the tag question (18), there should be a pause before the negator, and between *shi* and *ma* can be inserted a demonstrative, this or that. Also, the intonation is often rising at the end. These characteristics are not present on (17c). In (17c), there is no pause between before the NNN, and the sentence has a falling intonation in the end.⁴

- (18) Tā yǐjīng zǒu-le, bú-shì ((zhèyàng/ nàyàng)) ma? (↗)
 3SG already leave-PERF NEG-COP this that PRT
 'He already left, didn't he?'

4. Predictions and Consequences

The NNN construction must involve a cleft. Therefore, it is predicted that because of the unlocal configuration, the NNN does not interact with the contents in the lower CP. This section list several such predictions that the Neg-Cleft analysis correctly bears out.⁵

First, there is no selectional relationship between the NNN and the predicate. Two items are used for negation in Mandarin, *bù* and *méi*.⁶ As shown in (19), the predicate *xǐhuān* 'like' in (19a) is negated by *bù* instead of *méi*, but the possessive predicate *yǒu* in (19b) must be negated by *méi* instead of *bù*. If one really wants to use *bù* with (19b), (overt) clefting with the copula *shì* is obligatory as in (19c). However, the NNN is always realised as *bu* regardless of the kind of the predicate following it. That the NNN heads a CopP and ignores the predicate in the lower CP nicely captures this phenomenon.

- (19) a. Tā (<✓**bù**/ ***méi**) -xǐhuān zhè běn shū.
 3SG NEG NEG -like this CL_{book} book
 'He does not like this book.'
 b. Tā (<***bù**/ ✓**méi**) -yǒu zhè běn shū.
 3SG NEG NEG -be this CL_{book} book
 'He does not have this book.'
 c. ✓ Tā **bú-shì** yǒu zhè běn shū, érshì ...
 3SG NEG-COP be this CL_{book} book instead
 'It is not the case that he has this book; instead ...'
 (20) Tā (<✓**bù**/***méi**) -xǐhuān/yǒu zhè běn shū (ma).
 3SG NNN -like/be this CL_{book} book PRT
 'He likes/has this book. +M'

⁴ Holmberg's (2016) analysis of English tag questions may apply to (18).

⁵ Examples involving the NNN in this section will not include *shì*, which is in order to show that the cleft is there even with no overt copula.

⁶ See Liu & Li (2021) for a discussion of *bù* and *méi*.

(25) *Tā **bu** xìnghǎo zǒu-le
 3SG NEG fortunately leave-PERF
 *‘He did not fortunately leave.’

(26) Tā **bu** [CP xìnghǎo zǒu-le] (ma).
 3SG NNN fortunately leave-PERF PRT
 ‘He fortunately left. +M.’ ↔ PPI licensed in the positive CP

The phenomenon just described is strongly reminiscent of cartography — high adverbs sit at the Spec of respective functional heads that project in a fixed order in syntax (Cinque 1999). In fact, we can see that the NNN can precede any high adverbs except speech-act ones like *lǎoshíshuō* “honestly speaking”; besides, when stranded, the NNN follow various high heads. One might be pushed to propose the NNN is a head in the left periphery, but the analysis pursued here refrains from this approach.

- (27) (*) denotes a place illicit for *bu(-shì)* to appear in; > denotes *higher than*
- a. (*)Lǎoshíshuō **bu(-shì)** xìnghǎo (*)jùshuō (*)yěxǔ (*)tā
 honestly-speaking NNN(-COP) fortunately alledgedly probably 3SG
 zǒu-le.
 leave-PERF
 ‘Honestly speaking, fortunately, alledgedly, probably, he left. +M’
 - b. Tā yǐngjīng qù-le xuéxiào(*)le (*)éryǐ (*)deshuō **bu*?(-shì)**.
 3SG already go-PERF school S.ASP only EVID NNN*?(-COP)
 ‘It’s said that it’s only that it happened that he already went to the school. +M’
 - c. Speech-Act>NNN>Evaluative>Evidential/Epistemic/*Only*/Sentential.Aspect

Let’s temporarily take a step back and think about why in negation is incompatible with the evaluative adverb in (25). Ernst (2008:77) takes a semantic approach (28) to account for it. As seen in (28), he argues that value of “fortunately”, for example, has two components after it takes a proposition *p*: ① It presupposes that the proposition *p* is true in the *Belief Model* of the Speaker (MB(s)), and ② *p* is fortunate in every world that is compatible with what the speaker believes. Therefore, there is a contradiction between the first component of NEG(FORTUNATE(*p*)) and the negation. Indeed, using the definition of NEG by Collins & Postal (2014) as shown in (29a), by simple boolean logic, we could get the value of NEG(FORTUNATE(*p*)) in (29b). (29b①) cannot be achieved or otherwise contradiction will arise, but it is not obviously clear why the job of negation cannot be done through (29b②). This is possibly due to the fact that the second component in (28) concerns the judgment (Krifka 2021) of the speaker towards the proposition on the discourse level, and thus cannot be negated too locally to the propositional domain. Instead, it may be negated in a more unlocal way — metalinguistically, as a metalinguistic negator typically does not care what is happening under there. Actually, sentences including *xìnghǎo* “fortunately” can be negated metalinguistically with the help of clefting, shown in (30).

(28) $\llbracket \text{FORTUNATE}(p) \rrbracket = \textcircled{1} \llbracket p \rrbracket$ in $M_B(s)$
 $\textcircled{2} \llbracket \text{It is fortunate that } p. \rrbracket^w = 1 \forall w \in M_B(s)$. (ERNST 2008:77)

(29) a. If X has a semantic type ending in t , then
 NEG takes X with semantic value $\lambda P_1 \dots \lambda P_n [\dots]$
 and returns Y with semantic value $\lambda P_1 \dots \lambda P_n \neg[\dots]$

b. $\llbracket \text{NEG}(\text{FORTUNATE}(p)) \rrbracket = \begin{cases} \text{EITHER} & \textcircled{1} \exists w \in M_B(s) \text{ s.t. } \llbracket p \rrbracket^w = 0 \\ \text{OR} & \textcircled{2} \exists w \in M_B(s) \text{ s.t. } \llbracket \text{It is fortunate that } p. \rrbracket^w = 0 \end{cases}$

(30) Contexts: Zhāngsān and Lǐsì have a colleague that always causes troubles for them in work. One day this annoying colleague is fired. Zhāngsān is exuberant about his departure, and utters this sentence to Lǐsì.

?Tā **bú-shì** [xìngǎo]_F zǒu-le, tā **shì** [xìng<tāmāde-dà>hǎo]_F zǒu-le.
 3SG NEG-COP fortunately leave-PERF 3SG COP fortunately<f*cking-big> leave-PERF
 ‘It is not the case that he FORTUNATELY left; he SO FORTUNATELY left.’

As for the NNN construction, thanks to the cleft, it is compatible with the PPI as seen in (26). Is the NNN a metalinguistic negator? In fact, it passes all the relevant tests given by Martins (2014), listed in (31).

- (31) Standard Tests for Metalinguistic Negation Markers: (MARTINS 2014:4)
- No being embedded in subordinated clauses.
 - No licensing negative polarity items;
 - Compatibility with (strong) positive polarity items;
 - Requirement of the licensing by discourse/pragmatic contexts;

However, the paper sticks to NNN instead of metalinguistics negator for terminological consistency. Nor do I make use of the term high negation versus low negation (Holmberg 2016). *Bú-shì* is sometimes thought to be a high-negator (Erlewine 2017), which makes sense only relatively. (32) suggests that although the middle *bú-shì* is high compared to the low *bù*, it is relatively low compared to the NNN that is even higher.

(32) Tā **bu(-shì)** **bú-shì** **bù-xǐhuān** chī shuǐguǒ (ma).
 3SG NNN(-COP) NEG-COP NEG-like eat fruit PRT
 ‘It is not the case that he does not like eating fruits. +M’

Now I elaborate on the point mentioned in §3. The NNN is primitively the same item as the general negator *bù*. It negates over the proposition that might contain judgements by the speaker. However, the negation is later cancelled, in a pragmatic sense, by a silent intersubjective operator *NANDAO* “truly”, which some speakers can even pronounce overtly, at MoodP.^{8,9} Up to this point, the NNN construction seems parallel to biased questions. Compare (33a) with (33b). One may wonder, are

⁸ Mystically, some speakers can pronounce *náodào* after *bu(-shì)*, which I offer no explanation for.

⁹ *NANDAO* is difficult to translate. It literally means “difficult-say” and is used in *Yes-No* questions (Huang 2014).

the two *ma*'s the same? Yes. I argue that they are both instantiation of Force^o that types a clause as interrogative (PAN 2022).

- (33) a. Tā [MoodP NANDAO **bu(-shì)** yǐjīng zǒu-le] (**ma**). ↘
 3SG NNN(-COP) already leave-PERF PRT
 'He already left. +M' ~>NNN
- b. Tā (**nándào**) **bú-shì** yǐjīng zǒu-le (**ma**)? ↗
 3SG truly NEG-COP already leave-PERF Q
 'Didn't he leave??' ~>biased question

One Shanghainese speaker (Zhang 2023, p.c.) points out that the *ma* in (33a) should not be treated identically with the interrogative particle, since Shanghainese utilises two distinct sentence final particles for the NNN construction and for questions, displayed in (34).¹⁰

- (34) a. i vəʔ-z iɕin tsɿ-le? **ma**.
 3SG NEG-COP already leave-PERF PRT
 'He already left. +M'
- b. i iɕin tsɿ-le? **va**?
 3SG already leave-PERF Q
 'Did he leave?'

However, Shanghainese lacks a counterpart to the Mandarin *ma* in the first place. Whilst both *ma* and *va* are the 'default' particles to use with a *Yes-No* question in Mandarin and Shanghainese respectively, *ma* applies to both positive and negative questions (35a) but *va* is for positive questions only, seen in (36a). Notice that the Shanghainese *va* seems like *vəʔ+a*, a composite that contains a negator, so the *Neg Neg constraint bars it from abutting a negative *vP*. That the Mandarin *bù* also attaches only to positive questions as in (35b) corroborates this argument.¹¹ In contrast, the Mandarin *ma*, while etymologically related to negation (Schuessler 2007), has moved outside of the *vP* domain in history (Aldridge 2011). Therefore, (34) is illusionary and cannot suggest that the *ma* in NNN constructions is different from the question *ma*.

- (35) a. Tā (**bù**-)xǐhuān chī shuǐguǒ **ma**? (*ma* possible with negative questions)
 3SG NEG-like eat fruit PRT
 'Does he (not) like eating fruits?'
- b. Tā (***bù**-)xǐhuān chī shuǐguǒ **bù**? (*bù* impossible with negative questions)
 3SG NEG-like eat fruit NEG ~>meaning = (35a)
- (36) a. i (***vəʔ**-)hwœɕi tɕʰi? ʃku **va**? (*va* impossible with negative questions)
 3SG NEG-like eat fruit Q ~>meaning = (35a)
- b. i vəʔ-hwœɕi tɕʰi? ʃku **a**? (forced use of another particle a)
 3SG NEG-like eat fruit PRT
 'Does he not like eating fruits?'

¹⁰ In Shanghainese, the copula *z* is usually required as overt after the NNN *vəʔ*.

¹¹ See Cheng et al. (Cheng, Huang & Tang 1997) for an analysis of VP-Neg question.

As the two *ma*'s in (33a) and (33b) are both the question *ma*, how can the two sentences be distinguished? Note that what was previously thought to be ForceP (Rizzi 1997) can be dissected into two distinct layers that encode the clause type and the illocutionary force (Tang 2022). The sentence final *ma* and the fact that some speakers can even overly pronounce the operator *NANDAO* suggest that (33a) is firstly typed as interrogative. What it has in addition is an SAP projection that sets the illocutionary force as assertive and effects the falling intonation.

The analysis thus has an implication that the NNN construction originated from biased questions. Nonetheless, it is especially noted that the sentence (33b) that gave rise to the NNN construction is merely a special instance of biased questions — a general biased question need not contain either a cleft or negation. As seen in (37), a biased question of the form *nandao(p)* is licensed when the speaker is biased toward $\neg p$, no matter whether *p* contains negation. The response is based on the truth value of *p*. But things become divergent, with regard to the response pattern, when a biased question contains a Neg-cleft. In (38) the response is based on the truth value of a domain that *includes* the Neg-cleft. In (39), however, the response is based on a domain that *excludes* the Neg-cleft.¹²

- (37) a. Tā nándào [zǒu-le] ma??
 3SG truly [leave-PERF] Q
 ‘Did he truly leave??’ ~→biased toward ‘he did not leave’
 Response: “Yes, he left.” OR “No, he didn’t leave.”
- b. Tā nándào [méi zǒu] ma??
 3SG truly [NEG.PERF leave] Q
 ‘Did he truly not leave??’ ~→biased toward ‘he left’
 Response: “Yes, he didn’t leave.” OR “No, he left.”
- (38) A. Tā nándào [bú-shì yǐjīng zǒu-le] ma??
 3SG truly [NEG-COP already leave-PERF] Q
 ‘Is it truly *not* the case that he already left?’ ~→biased toward ‘he left’
- B. Mm, tā bú-shì yǐjīng zǒu-le.
 yep 3SG NEG-COP already leave-PERF
 ‘Yep, it is *not* the case that he already left.’ ~→response to A
- (39) A. Tā nándào bú-shì [yǐjīng zǒu-le] ma??
 3SG truly NEG-COP [already leave-PERF] Q
 ‘Didn’t he truly already left??’ ~→biased toward ‘he left’
- B. Mm, tā yǐjīng zǒu-le.
 yep 3SG already leave-PERF
 ‘Yep, he already left.’ ~→response to A

¹² (38A) and (38B) are in fact a bit different in prosody. In (38A), *bú-shì* might be stressed, whilst in (38B), *bú-shì* must not be stressed.

As indicated by the boxed areas above, in all (37a), (37b) and (38), whatever follows *nándào* “truly” is inside the domain on whose truth value the answer is based, whilst (39) differs from them in that the Neg-cleft *bú-shì* is not inside the domain. I propose a feature on Mood^o, marked by the emoji ☹️, to account for the contrast between (38) and (39).

As for the NNN construction, it is verified in (40) that the Neg-cleft is not included in the domain which the response is based on, which means that the NNN construction should have stemmed from the special instance of biased questions that has a Neg-cleft and [+☹️] on Mood^o. The discussion of biased questions and the NNN construction’s origin is summarised in the (41).¹³

(40) A. Tā [MoodP NANDAO [Mood^o ☹️ bu(-shì) yǐjīng zǒu-le]] (ma).
 3SG NNN-COP already leave-PERF PRT
 ‘He already left. +M’

B. Mm, tā yǐjīng zǒu-le.

yep 3SG NEG-COP already

Response: ‘Yes, he already left.’

(41) Biased Question (at ForceP)
 Neg-cleft present?

A final point needs to be addressed before coming to the ultimate refined analysis. Both ☹️ Neg-clefted biased questions and NNN constructions comfortably allow for evaluative, evidential and epistemic adverbs in the lower CP, as seen in (42). However, it is not the case for biased questions without ☹️ such as those in (37) and (38). I propose that it is this ☹️ that enables an intersubjective process that publicises not only the proposition but also the information encoded by the judgment-related (Krifka 2021) high adverbs (if any) along with it. The speaker expects that the speech participants should agree to all the publicised contents. If ☹️ is present, any judgmental high adverbs should be embedded under the Neg-cleft. Speech-act adverbs, however, are not judgmental, and hence they cannot be scoped under the NNN. For example, *lǎoshìshuō* “honestly speaking” expresses the speaker’s integrity at the utterance, and it is impossible for the addressee(s) to agree to or relate themselves to it. Seen in (43), it should be put not after the Neg-cleft but rather at the beginning of the sentence, scoping over everything.

¹³ Though the motivation of the proposal of the feature [+☹️] is to distinguish two kinds of Neg-clefted biased questions that have opposite response patterns, it is not said that the feature is only found in Neg-clefted biased questions. Nonetheless, it might be so. The feature [+assert], on the other hand, is clearly not dependent on . It is present as long as a sentence has assertive illocutionary force.

- (42) a. Tā [_{MoodP} nándào ☹ bú-shì ⟨xìnghǎo/ jùshuō/ yěxǔ⟩ yǐjīng zǒu-le] ma??
 3SG truly NEG-COP fortunately/allegedly/probably already leave-PERFQ
 ‘Didn’t he fortunarily/allegedly/probably already leave??’
- b. Tā [_{MoodP} ☹ bu(-shì) ⟨xìnghǎo/ jùshuō/ yěxǔ⟩ yǐjīng zǒu-le] (ma).
 3SG NNN(-COP) fortunately/allegedly/probably already leave-PERF PRT
 ‘He fortunarily/allegedly/probably already left. +M’
- (43) ^{OK}{Lǎoshíshuō} tā [_{MoodP} ☹ bu(-shì) *{lǎoshíshuō} yǐjīng zǒu-le] (ma).
 honestly-speaking 3SG NNN(-COP) already leave-PERF PRT
 ‘Honestly speaking, he already left. +M’

The graph in (44) summarises the analysis of the NNN construction. The proposition starts out in the lower CP which might contain high adverbs. Subsequently the Neg-cleft, the Mood head with ☹ and the interrogative Force head come in, forming temporarily a interrogative clause “Is it truly not the case that ... ??” that parallels a biased question. Finally, the SA head turns the sentence into an assertive illocution.

5. Conclusions and Discussions

The paper syntactically investigates the NNN construction and argues for a Neg-cleft analysis. The cleft is always there even when the copula is not overtly pronounced based on multiple pieces of evidence that the NNN is unlocal to the proposition. It also argues that the NNN is the same item as the general negator and the non-negativeness is due to its position and the licensing of a Mood head. It is also shown that the NNN construction should have stemmed from a special instance of biased questions because of the parallelity.

Unsolved problems remain. There is desired to be an answer to when the copula can and cannot be silenced as the syntactic position of the NNN varies, as shown in (2). Why it is possible for the copula in the NNN construction to be silent is interesting in the first place, since the power of the NNN construction to silence copulae seems only too power. Consider the sentence in (45a). There are two copulae, one after the NNN and one inside the lower CP. Both can be silent. Yet the copula is normally obligatorily overt in copular constructions as shown in (45b).

- (45) a. Zhè wèi bu(-shì) [CP *pro* (shì) tā zuì xǐhuān de lǎoshī] (ma).
 this CL_{person} NEG-COP COP 3SG most like DE teacher PRT
 ‘This person is his favourite teacher. +M’.
- b. Zhè wèi (bu) *(shì) tā zuì xǐhuān de lǎoshī. (obligatory shì)
 this CL_{person} NEG COP 3SG most like DE
 ‘This person is (not) his favourite teacher.’

Sometimes the copula is preferably covert, even for those who normally do not like to silence the copula. In (46), the NNN and the adverb *jiù* ‘right’ or *yě* ‘also’ are better not separated by an overt *shì*. There are also dialectal variations. In Shanghainese, ‘right’ tolerates a covert copula before it whilst ‘also’ prefers an overt one, as (47) shows (Zhang 2023, *p.c.*).

- (46) Tā bu(?-shì) [CP (jiù/yě) shì wǒmén zài zhǎo de rén] (ma).
 3SG NNN-(COP) right/also COP 1PL PROG look-for DE person PRT.
 (shì better covert)
 ‘He is right/also the person we are looking for. +M’
- (47) a. i vəʔ(-z) [CP dʒɿ z ə la ləʔləʔ zɿ ə niŋ] ma.
 3SG NNN-(COP) right COP 1PL PROG look-for DE person PRT.
 (z either overt or covert)
 ‘He is right the person we are looking for. +M’
- b. I vəʔ*(-z) [CP hɿ z ə la ləʔləʔ zɿ ə niŋ] ma. (z overt)
 3SG NNN-(COP) also COP 1PL PROG look-for DE person PRT
 ‘He is also a person we are looking for. +M’

Another question concerns the sentence final particle *ma*. Not everyone likes the omission of an overt *ma* in the NNN construction. These questions should be closely related to the module of phonology, which I leave to further research.

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